

FORM Nº: _____

DATE: ___/___/___

AGE: _____

SEX: M () F ()

SCHOOL LEVEL: _____

SCHOOL: _____

Public () Private ()

PERGUNTAS	RESPOSTAS		
Did you read in the newspaper that the UV index forecast is 7? Do you think that this radiation level is:	a) Low; b) Medium; c) High; d) Very High; e) Extreme; f) I don't know		
When do you use sunscreen?	a) Whenever I leave the house; b) Only when I go outdoors to walk, play sports, etc.; c) Only when I go to the beach or pool; d) Other situations; _____ e) I don't use sunscreen		
How do you use sunscreen?	a) I apply it only before exposing myself to the sun; b) I apply it only when I start to feel the sun heat my skin; c) I apply it before exposing myself to the sun and reapply it while I am exposed; d) I apply only when I feel I starting to get burned; e) I do not apply sunscreen		
When you use sunscreen, what is the sun protection factor (SPF)?	FPS →		I don't use sunscreen
Do you wear any kind of hats or caps when you are outdoors?	Yes	No	Sometimes
Do you wear sunglasses?	Yes	No	Sometimes
Are your sunglasses UV rated?	Yes	No	I don't know
Do you wear long-sleeved shirts to protect yourself from the sun?	Yes	No	Sometimes
Do you think a tan is beautiful and healthy?	Yes	No	I don't know
Of all the diseases listed below, which are caused by excessive sun exposure?			
Low immunity	Yes	No	I don't know
Skin cancer	Yes	No	I don't know
Eye diseases (cataracts)	Yes	No	I don't know
Premature aging (wrinkles)	Yes	No	I don't know
Skin blemishes (freckles and spots)	Yes	No	I don't know

Check the answers that best match your characteristics. Afterwards, note the sum of the score of each table in the place indicated at the bottom of the page, so that we can determine your skin phototype.

	0	1	2	3	4
TABLE 1: GENETIC DISPOSITION (DG)					
Color of your eyes	Light blue, grey or green	Blue, grey or green	Light brown	Dark brown	Brownish black
Natural color of your hair	Sandy red	Blond	Chestnut/dark blond	Dark brown	Black
Color of your skin in the non-exposed areas	Reddish	Very pale	Pale with beige tint	Light brown	Dark brown
Do you have freckles in the non-exposed areas ?	Many	Several	Few	Incidental	None
TABLE 2: REACTION TO SUN EXPOSURE (SE)					
What happens when you stay in sun too long?	Painful redness, blistering, peeling	Blistering followed by peeling	Burns sometimes followed by peeling	Rare burns	Never had burns
To what degree do you turn brown?	Hardly or not at all	Light color tan	Reasonable tan	Tan very easy	Turn dark brown quickly
Do you turn brown within several hours after sun exposure?	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Always
How does your face react to the sun?	Very sensitive	Sensitive	Normal	Very resistant	Never had a problem
TABLE 3: TANNING HABITS (TH)					
When did you last expose the body to sun (or artificial tanning)?	More than 3 months ago	2-3 months ago	1-2 months ago	Less than a month ago	Less than 2 weeks ago
Did you expose the area to be treated to the sun?	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Always

TABLE 1 POINTS: GENETIC DISPOSITION (DG)
TABLE 2 POINTS: REACTION TO SUN EXPOSURE (SE)
TABLE POINTS 3: TANNING HABITS (TH)
TOTAL SCORE (DG + SE + TH)

POINTS
 0 – 7
 8 – 16
 17 – 25
 26 – 30
 > 30

PHOTOTYPE
 I
 II
 III
 IV
 V – VI

**YOUR
PHOTOYPE**

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